

**Indira School of
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**TITLE : DISPLAY MARKETING ON ONLINE MEDIA PLATFORM
AND ITS EFFECTS ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR.**

Authors

**Dr. Atul Kumar, Mr. Apoorv Dalal, Mr. Chirantan Konwar,
Mr. Mayank Agrawal,
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Abstract

This paper summarizes the display advertising literature, organizing the content by the agents in the display advertising ecosystem, and proposes new research directions. In doing so, we take an interdisciplinary view, drawing connections among diverse streams of theoretical and empirical research in information systems, marketing, economics, operations, and computer science. By providing an integrated view of the display advertising ecosystem, we hope to bring attention to the outstanding research opportunities in this economically consequential and rapidly growing market.

Keywords:

Display Advertising, Online Platform, Literature Review, Real-Time Data

**TITLE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CONSUMER PERCEPTION
TOWARD CHINESE AND INDIAN ELECTRONIC ITEMS**

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Abstract

Atmanirbhar Bharat focuses on making our country self-reliant. Thus, the government is promoting various businesses to come up with innovative products and services. Due to government policies small and medium enterprise may witness very favourable environment. In few years Indian small and medium organization may come up with very good electronic products and which may become a competitive alternative to foreign electronic brands which are currently dominating the market. However, it is very important to investigate if